

ANALYSIS OF THE ELECTRICAL CONSUMPTION OF AN AIR-COOLED SINGLE EFFECT AMMONIA/WATER CHILLER

Summary

The electrical consumption of the air-cooled Robur ammonia/water absorption, model ACF60-00 LB, powered by hot water, has been studied. In particular, the effect of the chilled water temperature, the feed water temperature and the outdoor temperature on the electrical consumption of the chiller has been evaluated. For that objective, an analytical mathematical model has been implemented. The model is based on mass, species and energy balances. Results shows the existence of unfavorable working conditions when the electrical consumption reaches a maximum

Keywords: solar cooling; electrical consumption, ammonia-water; absorption chiller; ASTEP Project

1. Introduction

Heat supply system based on absorption heat pump have great potentials on energy saving and emission reduction due to it can be powered by waste thermal energy and solar energy, reducing notable electricity consumption. The most common working fluid in absorption refrigeration cycles able to achieve subzero cooling temperatures is the ammonia/water pair. The European ASTEP project is being developed within this framework, and one of its main objectives is to demonstrate the feasibility of the application of solar thermal energy to partially cover the cooling demands at an industrial site, the MANDREKAS dairy company, with a cooling demand at 5°C. Within that project, the present work aims to study the feasibility and main constrains to use a commercial air-cooled ammonia/water absorption chiller driven by a patented solar concentrator (sun dial) to satisfy the MANDREKAS's cooling demand at different outdoor conditions.

A key feature of the air-cooled absorption chillers is its electrical consumption, which should be minimized in order that to be competitive to the vapor compressors of similar cooling capacity (Izquierdo et al., 2012). In order to evaluate the electrical consumption of the air-cooled chilled when operating in different conditions, the main components of the chiller, namely, distillation column, air-cooled absorber, evaporator and condenser, have been modeled by implementing a discrete model, and subsequently integrated to the whole chiller.

This study analyzes the electric consumption required to cool down the air-cooled absorber and condenser, beside the electric consumption of the solution pump.

2. Mathematical model

Mass and energy conservation balances, in addition to the most appropriate experimental mass and heat transfer correlations for the ammonia/water absorption chiller (Sieres et al. 2007), have been implemented to model the behavior of the different components of the ammonia/water absorption chiller. The Engineering Equation Solver has been the software used. The film theory was applied to mass and transfer equations in every differential control volume. In addition, the definition of effectiveness for every heat exchanger has been applied (Kim et al. 2008). As a result, the required air-cooling mass flow rate has been obtained for the operation conditions studied, namely, temperature of the hot feed water (160°C and 210 °C), chilled water temperature (-5°C and 0°C) and outdoor temperature (from 10°C to 45°C).

3. Results

The amount of rejected energy to the ambient for the air-cooled absorber chiller depends mainly on the outdoor temperature, and the temperature of the chilled and feed water, which determine not only the coefficient of performance of the chiller but also its cooling capacity. Fig. 1 shows the cooling capacity and the coefficient of performance of the Robur chiller model ACF-60 00-LB for the different operation conditions analyzed here. Since the amount of rejected energy increases as the cooling capacity increases and the coefficient of

performance decreases, it is expected the existence of some working condition when the energy rejected reaches a maximum value, and so, the electrical consumption of the ancillary equipment. Similar behavior it is expected to be for the solution pump, as it is shown in Fig. 2. On the other hand, the energy rejection to the ambient takes place through the solid wall of the external heat exchanger (condenser, absorber), which geometry is invariable for every operating condition. Therefore, the required amount of rejected energy is managed mainly by varying the air-cooling mass flow rate, and so, the electrical energy consumption of the ancillary equipment that cools down absorber and condenser.

Fig. 1: Cooling capacity and coefficient of performance of the hot water fired air-cooled single effect ammonia/water chiller (Robur chiller model ACF-60 00-LB). Hot water temperature: 160 - 210 °C. Chilled water temperature: -5°C – 0°C

Fig. 2: Electrical power consumption of the solution pump. Hot water temperature: 160 - 210 °C. Chilled water temperature: -5°C – 0°C

Figures 3 and 4 show the electrical power consumption of ancillary equipment that cools down absorber and condenser. Results agree with typical value for absorption chillers of similar cooling capacity (Zamora et. Al, 2014). Results shows the existence of unfavorable working conditions when the electrical consumption reaches a maximum.

Fig. 3: Electrical power consumption of the ancillary equipment of the air-cooled absorber. Hot water temperature: 160 - 210 °C. Chilled water temperature: -5°C – 0°C

Fig. 4: Electrical power consumption of the ancillary equipment of the air-cooled condenser. Hot water temperature: 160 - 210 °C. Chilled water temperature: -5°C – 0°C

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